

A, Profile:1 Confidence: 1

B

A, Profile:2 Confidence: 1

B

A, Profile:5 Confidence: 1

B

A, Profile:6 Confidence: 1

B

A, Profile:8 Confidence: 1

B

A, Profile:9 Confidence: 1

B

A, Profile:14 Confidence: 1

B

A, Profile:15 Confidence: 1

B

A, Profile:16 Confidence: 1

B

A, Profile:24 Confidence: 1

B

A, Profile:25 Confidence: 1

B

A, Profile:26 Confidence: 1

B

A, Profile:28 Confidence: 1

B

A, Profile:31 Confidence: 0.5

B

A, Profile:34 Confidence: 1

B

A, Profile:35 Confidence: 0.5

B

A, Profile:36 Confidence: 0.5

B

A, Profile:39 Confidence: 0.5

B

A, Profile:41 Confidence: 0.5

B

A, Profile:43 Confidence: 0.5

B

A, Profile:47 Confidence: 1

B

A, Profile:48 Confidence: 0.5

B

A, Profile:50 Confidence: 0.5

B

A, Profile:52 Confidence: 0

B

A, Profile:54 Confidence: 0.5

B

A, Profile:55 Confidence: 0.5

B

A, Profile:56 Confidence: 1

B

A, Profile:59 Confidence: 0.5

B

A, Profile:66 Confidence: 0

B

A, Profile:67 Confidence: 0

B

A, Profile:69 Confidence: 0

B

A, Profile:71 Confidence: 0

B

A, Profile:72 Confidence: 0

B

A, Profile:74 Confidence: 0

B

A, Profile:76 Confidence: 0

B

A, Profile:77 Confidence: 0

B

A, Profile:79 Confidence: 0

B

A, Profile:80 Confidence: 0.5

B

A, Profile:81 Confidence: 0.5

B

A, Profile:87 Confidence: 0.5

B

A, Profile:90 Confidence: 1

B

A, Profile:93 Confidence: 1

B

A, Profile:103 Confidence: 0.5

B

